

A TIME TRANSFER TECHNIQUE USING A SPACE-BORNE HYDROGEN MASER AND
LASER PULSE TIMING

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Abstract

We describe a system for worldwide precision time transfer between ground-based clocks and a satellite-borne clock, using laser pulse timing. The system is designed to compare time between earth and space clocks with a precision of 100 ps or better, and will be tested as part of the NASA/SAO Hydrogen Maser Clock experiment, which is currently under construction.

Time Transfer Technique

As part of the NASA/SAO Hydrogen Maser Clock (HMC) experiment, we have developed a system for high-precision time transfer between space-borne and earth-based clocks, using laser pulse timing. When used with a hydrogen maser in an earth-orbiting spacecraft, this technique promises time comparisons with a precision of 100 ps or better worldwide. The HMC experiment will test this system, together with an active hydrogen maser designed for use in space, for a period of approximately six months on a spacecraft with an altitude of about 500 km.

In this system, time kept by a clock located at an earth-based laser ranging station (LRS) is compared with the space clock's time by measuring the arrival time of a laser pulse at the spacecraft in terms of both the space and earth time scales. A laser pulse transmitted from the LRS is detected at the spacecraft and its arrival time t_s is determined in terms of the space clock's time by a high-speed electronic interpo-

lation circuit called an event timer. The pulse is also reflected by a retroreflector array mounted on the spacecraft and is received at the LRS as a return pulse. Its transmission and return times, t_{1e} and t_{2e} , are measured in terms of the earth clock's time by an event timer located in the LRS. The time difference Δt between the earth and space clocks is then given by $\Delta t = t_s - (t_{1e} + t_{2e})/2$.

The main components of the time transfer system, which are shown schematically in Figure 1, are the retroreflector array; a fiber-optic light collector mounted on the retroreflector array; a photomultiplier tube and preamplifier; and the event timer, consisting of a constant-fraction discriminator and a high-resolution time interpolator. These components, as designed for the HMC experiment, are described below.

Retroreflector Array

The HMC retroreflector array consists of 20 fused silica cube corners, each 1 cm in diameter, mounted in a hemispherical base. This shape provides a hemispherical field of view, permitting reflections independent of spacecraft attitude. (Two reflector arrays mounted on opposite sides of the spacecraft provide complete spherical coverage.) The use of a relatively large number of small reflectors confers three advantages: (i) velocity aberration is accounted for by diffraction by the reflector's entrance pupil, allowing the reflecting surfaces to be manufactured with a dihedral angle of exactly 90°; (ii) the array can be made compact, approximately 6 cm in diameter, reducing the variation in centroid as a function of viewing angle; and (iii) the array's far-field intensity

pattern is uniform with angle, minimizing return intensity variations measured at the LRS.

Fiber Optic Light Collector and Photodetector

Laser pulses impinging on the retroreflector array are brought to a photomultiplier tube by an omnidirectional fiber optic light collector. The collector consists of a 22-cm long bundle of 127 optical fibers, each 200 μm in diameter. At one end of the bundle the fibers are splayed out into a hemispherical pattern and inserted through holes drilled in a 1.5-cm diameter hemispherical shell, as shown schematically in Figure 2. The fibers are epoxied in place within the shell, which is mounted at the apex of the retroreflector array. The other end of the fiber bundle connects to a photomultiplier tube (PMT) that detects the laser pulses. A focussing lens and a neutral density filter, located between the bundle and the PMT focus and attenuate the light, and a narrow-band interference filter eliminates ambient light away from the laser's 532 nm wavelength. A PMT was chosen as the photodetector because it has a large cathode area, which simplifies coupling the fibers to the detector, and a high gain that can be varied over a wide range, allowing adjustment to varying pulse intensities. The uniformity of the retroreflector array's return pattern with angle means that the distance offset between the light collector's centroid and the array's centroid is a function only of the incoming laser pulse's polar angle, and is independent of azimuth; this property simplifies the correction for spacecraft attitude.

Event Timer

The time transfer system's ability to resolve sub-nanosecond intervals results from a high-precision space-qualified event timer developed at the Los Alamos National Laboratory that is capable of timing with a resolution of 10 ps. The output pulse from the PMT is amplified by a preamplifier and sent to a constant-fraction discriminator (CFD), which produces a pulse whose shape is to largely independent of the input pulse amplitude [1-3]. This property of the CFD reduces the systematic variation in triggering time, called time walk, that would otherwise result from the orders-of-magnitude variation in

arriving laser pulse intensity that can result from changes in atmospheric conditions and in spacecraft attitude and altitude.

The CFD's output pulse goes to a time interpolator[4,5], which is a combined digital and analog circuit that interpolates the 100 MHz clock signal provided by the spacecraft's hydrogen maser. When a pulse triggers the time interpolator, a capacitor is charged by a constant current I_c until the next clock edge arrives. The capacitor is then discharged by a second constant current $I_d = -I_c/1000$, and the discharge time is measured in terms of clock periods. By this technique the interpolator divides the 10 ns clock period into 1000 "bins", providing 10 ps resolution.

We have built and tested brassboard versions of the photomultiplier and event timer circuits. The interpolator's integral linearity, which is a measure of the total timing error for any bin compared to a perfectly linear interpolator, is less than 10 ps, with test-to-test repeatability of less than 1 ps.

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Figure 1. Schematic view of time transfer system components

Fig 2. Schematic cutaway view of fiber-optic light collector shell. Two of 127 fibers shown.